

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND THEIR EFFECTS ON THE ADDED MASS

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ABSTRACT

Not long ago the zero added mass has been replaced by a none zero constant added mass in the marine, biological and other fields. A few people realized that both models are simply wrong. While the majority researchers believe the latter without any shred of **real** logic or evidence, there are new buds showing a movement toward the real world. Currently there is a new group of researchers who believe that the added mass changes occur without any physical reason. No one in that group can explain what are the physical roots (causes) to the change, yet this acknowledgment itself is a progress. There is a strong and abundant physically observed evidence and logical arguments showing that the added mass varies and even heavily used in the animal kingdom such as octopus maneuvering.

These small amount buds discussing the added mass change and attribute it to limited causes which are presented in this paper. A new cause for the added mass change is adjoined which explain several phenomena which were not possible to explain before. Furthermore, the added mass change affects the governing equations is discussed the effects which previously ignored.

The previous causes to the added mass change are the orientation change, volume change, movement in the phase change media, the body deformation (without volume change). In this paper, a new cause to the added mass change is presented which is another object or border.

NOMENCLATURE

A Cross Section Area
a Acceleration
C Boundary on body and object
E Energy (potential)

F Force
g Gravity constant
k Spring constant
m Mass
 \mathbb{M} Added Mass volume
S Boundary on the body or the object
t Time
U Velocity
u Local velocity
V Volume
x Distance or coordinate
y Distance perpendicular to *x*
z Distance perpendicular to *x*, and *y*

Greek Letters

Φ Velocity Potential
 ρ density
 θ angle

Subscript

0 main direction
1 one direction
2 second direction
3 third direction
i 1,2,3

Key Words

Added Mass Change, Moment of Inertia change Added Mass Energy Conservation, Added Mass Change Causes, Marine Navigation, Fish Locomotion

1 Introduction

The history added mass to some extent was described (Bar-Meir 2023a; Bar-Meir 2021). The specific history of the understating of the added mass change is minimally described for cause of the body volume change by (Giorgio-Serchi and Weymouth 2017) with considerable missing information on the origin etc. In the quest of finding information on the effects of the added mass change, it was realized that there is no grant understating and it spread over many locations. The added mass change due to the volume change discussed in several not related fields such as boiling (light body and heavy fluid), aquatic bodies locomotion, multi phase flow, external flow with chemical reactions (even stokes flow), etc. For the same cause of the added mass change, the people, from different point of view, saw a different “problem”. Of course the mechanism(s) is/are the same. The common effects were not examined in a uniform method. This realization occurred not that long ago.

As all new ideas at the problem at hand produce the living experiment of how evolution of ideas is at work. Almost sharp lines can be drawn and identified between several research groups. Like living fossil, there are still people who believe that no added mass exist or needed for the calculations. Their idea is based on the solution of Navier–Stokes equation which, according to them, is actually the solution of the problem. Thus, the integration of the pressure on the body is the force acting on the body (thus no need for added mass). At first glance, it seems reasonable only if one forget that fluid has to accelerate when the body is accelerated to replace its body place. Here, the marine engineering education has to be credited for eliminating this nonsense from most people.

One was expecting that this kind group to be in the zero size since the added mass was used for over 70 (maybe 94 years if considering van Karman) years as writing this paper. The fact that these papers which propel this idea are still accepted to journals is ultimate proof that this idea is still a live and kicking. Here is a small sample of this idea: Bianchi (2022) studied the Cownose Ray where is simply disregarded the added mass. It is not unique, another recent example is Zeng (2023). When the author asked about it, he stated “[t]he CFD directly solves the Navier–Stokes equations and the added mass is not needed in this model”. It seems that the author and others who hold this belief assume that somehow their program calculated the added mass (maybe by solving the NS equations which is wrong!) or simply ignored it (see (Ke, Tu, Goerig, Tan, Cheng, Li, and Shi 2022)). It is beyond amazing that some people aware of the added mass change and yet (Zhang, Ma, Shao, and Zhang 2023) when study phase change (they call it water entry) did realize that main mechanism to absorbed the energy is the added mass change. So they used none physical concept that has nothing to do with mechanism such as relaxation zones. Matharu et al (2023) believe because a software good for air planes (in low density gas) it must work in heavy liquid. According to them,

the commercial software even without added mass calculations dealing with jellyfish which has a volume change, and deflection the added mass can be ignored. With knowing whether the commercial software even have added mass calculations, how one use a black box. People who hold this fossil concept at least have the shame of not to advertising that this idea is their core belief. Additionally, one expect this nonsense to be eliminated from the downstream (in the standard undergraduate textbooks, and undergraduate material). Yet, even as recently several textbooks on ship stability even standard fluid mechanics deny the existence added mass (see GATE famous Indian test).

It is more common (the majority of a subjective study by this author about about 400 papers with over 380 holding this idea.) to see papers with the assumption of constant added mass (and constant moment of inertia). It is not clear who was the first to introduce the constant added mass assumption but it reasonable that it started from the inception of the introduction of the added mass. It is interesting that this absurd assumption is dominate the education and standard material. For example, the class in US naval academy, Judge (2019) is presenting this idea as the absolute true. When pointing to her these errors in this approach (There are several papers by Judge with this mistake and similar errors but different mistakes which results in wrong conclusions. This fact is what one should expect from those who are teaching these errors.) she stated “I am trying to write a set of course notes that helps my students understand the concepts they will need in the future.” It should be accepted that it is vital importance for the students’ understanding by teaching erroneous material. When pointing to her by a clear physical example that demonstrates her explanations are erroneous and the errors are clearly exposed, she just ignores it. Other advocates of this erroneous method are (Fossen 2011; Techet 2005) seem to ignore the criticism which they are aware of. They are doing the disgraced Peter Hotez (The corona virus “scientist” exposed with lies and refuse to defend his claims in a million dollars to debate (for him) with RFK.).

One of the cause of the added mass change is orientation of the velocity relative to the ship to the main axes. For example, Alexandersson et al (2022) calculate the zig zag operation of the ship with a constant added mass. While the authors miss this point at least they had an open mind about it. The nature of the zig zag is to have the ship in a different orientation at different angle. Thus the added mass change during the zig zag maneuvering. This point was published on the “Stability of Ships and Other Bodies” around 2021 ignored by many and not realized by many even though it was explicitly discussed there.

The next step in the evolution is the group people who noticed either the pivot points are not in the place where the establishment alleged them to be (mass centroid) or the added mass is not constant without any physical expiation. While these two different issues seems to be different, yet because the change of pivot points will eventually leads to the realization of the change

of the added mass, they should be treated the same fashion. The two prominent cases are Zhu (2023) and Kanso et al (Kanso, Marsden, Rowley, and Melli-Huber 2005) in which the added mass was calculated without any physical model. The meaning physical model here is like calculating viscosity effect using Euler equations (Euler's equations ignore the viscous effect). You might get viscosity effect but it probably because an error in the numerical or logic manipulations. It does not make any difference one way or the other even five (5) references reviewed the paper which mentioned by Kanso or even a thousand scientists endorse this claim (on the opposite spectrum but actually the same, this author was ridiculed in past by many only to be found absolutely correct.). According the Zhu et al and Kanso et al the added mass is varied during the movement because the mathematical manipulation (Maybe different coordinate system produces different results. It is bury inside the code where no one can check.). In Kanso et al papers, as opposed to Zhu et al papers has several manipulations seems to violate physics laws if the writing should be understood according to the way it was written (maybe they meant something else)¹. In that case, maybe the variations of the added mass is not due to a real physical things but due to simple mathematical manipulations that might be or not be correct. But clearly according the Kanso's group and Zhu's group, nothing is based on a physical ground.

The following step occurred in parallel in which people noticed that when the body volume change it forces the added mass to follow the change. There are at least two reasons that trigger the investigations of the change of the added mass, one the examination of the locomotion of aquatic creatures and two bubbles due to boiling. Saffman (1967) who study the theoretical affect of the velocity potential due to expansion. Ohl (2003) study experimentally the change of the added mass due to change of bubble size. It is interesting to point that his equations (4) and (5) are conceptional erroneous because there should have more terms to describe the work. Ohl's study did not leave any real mark beside the idea itself. This idea was continue and emerged from the study of the bubble in boiling (Ueno, Nishita, and Kamiyama 1999) ignored the added mass. And yet, of course what else, for this model had a wholesome and wonderful experimental evidence (irony for experiments conflicting real science). Furthermore, one element of the implications was discussed in by Giorgio et al (2017). As it was discussed in (Bar-Meir 2023a) people were aware of the change in the added mass for example, Bainbridge's experiment (1963) his data showed that the value of added mass can be simplified as $m_a = 1/4 \pi / \rho d^2$, where d is the depth. Bainbridge measurements show that the added mass also depends on time. This fact demonstrates that fish's deformation

(and maybe the orientation) affects the added mass. Lighthill's data (1971) revealed that the added mass value (coefficient) is around one and it is fluctuating about 25%. It worth noting that the limit of the change of added mass in this case which is about 25%. This limit is a positive indication for the maximum extraction of energy (or momentum) by caudal fin (tail) which indirectly demonstrates the added mass change effect.

A string of papers dealing with the added mass change due to change of the volume mostly for a spherical shape appeared in the literature for example (Weymouth and Triantafyllou 2013; Weymouth, Subramaniam, and Triantafyllou 2015). In these papers the motivation was to understand how the octopus and/or aquatic bodies increase their speed in a critical maneuvering (hunting or hunted). In the said paper, the focus was on the theoretical aspects of the added mass change. Hence, attempt was made to understand the underlying principles behind the change of added mass. It was suggested that the added mass momentum (they referred to this as the lost differently) is "lost" when body added mass reduced and should be added as an external force on the right side (of the equations) for the body movement. This approach is the upper limit to maximum force obtained by the added mass change. While these authors did not realize it, they actually invented the added momentum concept.

During writing the book "stability of the ship and other bodies" (2022d, 2023b), this author realized that the added mass varies with the orientation. Later, the author was asked to investigate the roll motion. This investigation led to the observation that energy conservation does not occur (Bar-Meir 2023a). Thus, this combined works led to the idea that governing equations are effected by the orientation change. Notice this effect cannot described by the establishment equations used and shown in (Judge 2019). Since the body orientation (the body relative velocity direction to body orientation) is affecting the added mass, thus other causes of the added mass change affect as well. It follows that the deformation also changes the added mass and thus changes movement. The last statement is self evident. Navigation of surface vehicle (ship etc) creates a situation where the shape of the body changes and hence the added mass changes. For example, the change of the rudder angle change added mass.

2 Previous Methods

At this stage, when people such Saffman (1967) and the group of English group² suggested two methods to solve the problem. The first approach, Saffman suggested that the added mass change can be written as potential separably. Thus, the total

¹It is very hard for this author to read a paper when the author claims opposite what is written. It appears that something on right hand side to be constant only to be claimed by the authors to be on the left hand side and variable. One should expect this claims from only a Federal Judges like S. R. Nelson Minnesota.

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²which is neither English nor a group but nonetheless easy to remember.

FIGURE 1. Different causes of the added mass change. (a) due to change of the body form, (b) moving in and out liquid (c) change of volume, and (d) change of direction of the body.

velocity potential can be written as

$$\Phi_{total} = \Phi_T + \Phi_D \quad (1)$$

Symbol	Definition
Φ	potential
subscript	
D	deformation potential
T	translation potential
$total$	whole potential

This deformation potential is based on the velocity and not the acceleration. According to this idea the deformation potential is a beast that actually does not represent the core issue. Specifically, this idea does not capture the time dependence element of the added mass and hence it enforces the time derivative only on velocity. As this can be demonstrated by this example: theoretically body with a zero (small) volume with a large acceleration and zero velocity yield small or zero value while the transitional part should have a large value.

The English group suggested the model in which the added mass and the body locate in a system in vacuum (they did not referred to it as such but removing all the effects beside the added mass which actually means vacuum. The word system here has the thermodynamics meaning) (Bar-Meir 2023a). The added mass is actually based on the body and its changes. This approach captures the change due to the acceleration. In away this methods solved the main problem of the Saffman's deformation potential. The current literature review does not show any im-

provements to Saffman's approach and it seems, to this author, to be abandoned.

As the added mass change method of the English group has only a small amount of people aware of and accepting it (one can only wonder why? Good concept!). In fact, this approach is rejected by people who run the US naval academy and post naval academy and whole hosts in many locations. As prof. Judge stated "we do it for our students". The strange of all, one individual of the group itself reject or ignore this idea in different cases. This rejection is baseless. Perhaps the reason that this idea had insignificant effect (as it deserved) is because it was associated with almost exclusive single cause (the volume change). Thus, people did not see the general ramification of the issue.

The added mass change was built for different arguments not aware of the English group's idea and with the realization that body and added mass are not in vacuum (Bar-Meir 2023b). While this method is a significant improvement, there are several questions unsolved to the satisfaction of this author. The question integration of the body mass with the surroundings remained to some extend opened (which involve the difference between the fluid velocity neglecting the added mass and where one is considering the added mass). While understanding of work on the surroundings limit arguments or idea is gained, it is not fully solved and should be considered some what opened.

There are two additional causes that the added mass changes for different reasons. The first case if the phase change and it can be traced back all the way to 1929 (Von Karman 1929). In that case von Karman studied penetration of the body into water when air plane lands on water. The knowledge of the added mass at time was very limited and of course his assumptions are extremely crude (It is not that the situation today is much better in some respects of added mass. See for example the trapezoid body added mass is still considered to be unknown.). In fact, the added mass used in that derivations hardly resemble our understanding of the modern added mass. Yet, amazingly von Karman realized and he considered the full Newtons Law ($d(mU)/dt$ vs. $m dU/dt$). He had similar conceptual approach like the English group. There are several other papers in which the authors realized that due to the phase change the added mass changes. In that case, Li et al (2018) used the slender body theory to calculated the added mass variations. The corrections due to change of the added mass the slender body theory will be suggested down below. Both of these cases, they made crude calculations while neglecting important part(s). Yet, in the same time, both of them realize that the added mass change due to phase change is continuous and changing. As a demonstration of how significant and important the realization that added mass change consider recent work by Ortega et al (2022) when entry of body from a gas phase to liquid liquid and vis versa. While provided pictures are beautiful, numerous mistakes in the paper are ignored so the focus can be made on the added mass change. The core mechanisms of the absorbed kinetic energy is done by

the change of the added mass and increase of the contact angle for the surface tension. Missing these two mechanisms, as it is done in the said paper, renders the model worthless which is very common approach in the field. Thus, the added mass change provides the transitional mechanism to absorbed some energy which Ortega et al is missed.

Analyzing fish movement Paniccia et al (2022, 2021) used the different values for added mass for different deformed shape of the fish. Thus, in doing so, Paniccia recognized the deformation effects on the added mass. While Paniccia's group recognized the change of added mass, yet they used the old equations of the motion ($m dU/dt$ vs. $d(mU)/dt$). This recognition is not unique and so is the oblivion to effects on the governing equations. This oblivion suggests that there is a blind spot which effected almost all. It is hoped this this paper will be illuminate this point.

3 Additional Cause of the Added Mass Change

The above review dealt with previously recognized causes of the added mass change. With exception of the orientation, all discussed earlier in the literature but without the recognition of the effect on the governing equations. One of the limitations today that is recognized of numerical software commercial and academic) used the ability to capture the ship approaching to deck (dock?) or another ship (another object see fig. 2) (Zghyer 2023, page 36, ¶ 1). While all the software packages are actually contain so many errors and misunderstandings that all of them should go through a major overall.

FIGURE 2. Body with object in infinite medium

It is not surprising that the current software is not able to predict anything in particular when ship approach another ship or a deck. So what so special about this situation? Well, the added mass is changing. From physical point of view, the added mass increases because it harder to push liquid (water) around. In other words, more force is required to push when a boundary or other body is present. In this section several myths have to be busted and thus the repeat of material published in (Bar-Meir 2022d) is repeated and presented here for completeness. The first myth is that for added mass matrix $a_{ij} = a_{ji}$. It commonly believed that

the added mass matrix is symmetrical regardless boundary conditions. However, the requirement for this statement to be true is when the medium is infinity (boundary condition are at infinity) and no object (this point is very important). Otherwise in most cases, this statement is not correct. This fact can intuitively explained by the fact that velocity field changes when a body moves in a medium when there are objects. Or in the negative way, the object and the body moving in the same velocity and hence there the added mass matrix describing these two which can be considered as one body for which $a_{ij} = a_{ji}$. Thus splitting the two will not necessarily yield $a_{ij} = a_{ji}$. Thus breaking the body into two arbitrary bodies will not crate two symmetrical matrices. Thus when there is surface or (phase change in terminology of this paper) the added mass symmetry must in limited because the infinity b.c. requirement cannot be fulfilled.

The second myth is the idea that a body and added mass have to be supplied in order to determine the added mass. The actual situation because the elliptical (linear) characters of the idea flow can be separated into added mass for body and boundary at infinity and the effect of the object.

Before going through, there several physical observations should be pointed out in regards to the physics. Birds and school of fishes are organized in a certain pattern in which a strong individual leads in the front and the other riding behind in a pattern which gives maximum efficiency. Without dealing how the pattern is formed and its geometry, it widely accepted and measured that downstream creatures benefits while the payment is made the leading individuals. The common explanation is that vortices that detached from the body are responsible for these coupling (Bao and Tao 2014). That paper contains many common misconception, and yet it led to appearance of the force pulling leading fish. This idea conflicts with the fact that this vortices are not affected by the downstream conditions. The mechanism that the effects work is by the added mass through the new cause which discussed blow.

4 Boundary Condition Derivations

Consider a body and object (part that is not moving or moving in a different velocity "direction and speed") in an infinite medium without any viscosity. Thus the traditional definition of the velocity potential can be written as

$$U_i = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x_i} \tag{2}$$

where $i = x, y, \text{ and } z$ in Cartesian coordinates. Hence the total velocity potential is when all the three potentials are combines as

$$\phi = \phi_x + \phi_y + \phi_z \tag{3}$$

The definition of added mass is based on the added force which can be broken into three components, F_x , F_y , and F_z . The directional added mass is defined as

$$m_i = \frac{F_i}{a_i} \quad (4)$$

where $i = x, y, \text{ and } z$, and when no index is assigned is for the total.

Notice that the directional added mass as concept was first introduced in (Bar-Meir 2022d) which is the root of the added mass change due to orientation.

The kinetic energy in the field is

$$E = \frac{\rho_\ell}{2} \int_V ((u_1)^2 + (u_2)^2 + (u_3)^2) dV \quad (5)$$

where here E denotes the energy of the entire field and u_1 is the locale velocity in let say x the same for the other components (u_2 velocity in y and u_3 velocity in z or any other orthogonal coordinate system). Note, this statement is correct for any orthogonal system but requires the entire field/medium. Equation (5) will be differentiated (later) and transformed into

$$E = \frac{\rho_\ell U_0^2}{2} \mathbb{M} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbb{M} = \int_V \left(\left(\frac{u_1}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_2}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_3}{U_0} \right)^2 \right) dV \quad (7)$$

The value of the integral eq. (7) is independent of body velocity and every geometry and orientation can be evaluated. Note the medium volume has to be infinite in all directions. The meaning orientation in this context is the relationship of velocity components. Normally, the velocities ratio are selected so that they are in the main directions ($x, y, \text{ and } z$).

The derivative with respect to time of \mathbb{M} (or in other words, the added mass is fixed) is zero. In other words, there is no change as long as there is no object and medium is stretch to infinity.

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \rho U_0 \mathbb{M} \frac{dU_0}{dt} \quad (8)$$

The power needed to be supplied to the field to carry this change

has to be

$$power = F U_0 \quad (9)$$

The energy conservation requires that power supplied have to be equal to the change of the kinetic energy of the field where here, F is the force and U is the velocity, hence

$$F U_0 = \frac{dE}{dt} = \rho_\ell U_0 \mathbb{M} \frac{dU}{dt} \quad (10)$$

Canceling the velocity on both sides of eq. (10) Provides

$$F = \rho_\ell \mathbb{M} \frac{dU}{dt} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) can get the standard form $F = ma$ when $\rho_\ell \mathbb{M}$ is denoted the added mass. This added mass is not actual liquid mass but rather a representation of equivalent mass if it would be accelerated with the body. A entire fluid field is accelerated but not in the same neither uniform amount of amount. So, instead of doing the calculations for the entire field it is done for a simpler representation.

5 Boundary Condition Added Mass Change

FIGURE 3. Integration paths of Added Mass.

This section deals with the cause of the boundary condition for the change of the added mass. Some of the elements of the derivations were discussed earlier, however, the cause that changed was not. The potential function in fluid is a function which when a gradient is applied to it exhibits the velocity such that

$$\mathbf{U} = \nabla \phi \quad (12)$$

Which also implies that the Laplace equation ($\nabla^2\phi = 0$) is valid, when the flow is irrotational flow. First establishing an identity that will be used later. Utilizing differentiation Product Rule as

$$\iint_A \left(\frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial x} \right) dA = \iint_A \left(\phi_1 \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial x} - \phi_1 \frac{\partial^2\phi_2}{\partial x^2} \right) dA \quad (13)$$

first integral on the right hand side can be converted by utilizing Green's theory to be

$$\iint_A \left(\frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial x} \right) dA = \iint_C \left(\phi_1 \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial n} \right) dA - \iint_A \left(\phi_1 \frac{\partial^2\phi_2}{\partial x^2} \right) dA \quad (14)$$

if $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi$ than eq. (14) can be written as

$$\iint_A \left(\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right)^2 dA = \int_C \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA - \iint_A \left(\phi \frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial x^2} \right) dA \quad (15)$$

Three dimensional version (and notice $C = S_{in} + S_{out}$) of eq. (15) is

$$\iiint_V \left(\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right)^2 dV = \iint_{S_{in}+S_{out}} \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA - \iiint_V \phi \frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial x^2} dV \quad (16)$$

S_{in} denotes the boundary on the body and S_{out} denotes the boundary on other bodies (object or boundary) of the container that contain the body. To get the total kinetic energy the other two components should be included and become

$$\iiint_V \left[\left(\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\phi}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] dV = \iint_{S_{in}+S_{out}} \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA - \iiint_V \phi \left(\frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial z^2} \right) dV \quad (17)$$

The left hand side represent the kinetic energy in the domain bounded by the body and infinity. The right hand side represents the component that contribute to this integral. The first term on the right represents the perpendicular velocity at the bodies that is in the domain boundary. The second term vanishes because the Laplacian is zero inside the domain (continuity equation). What left on the right is split-ed into two components as

$$\iint_{S_{in}+S_{out}} \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA = \overbrace{\iint_{S_{in}} \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA}^{\text{on the body}} + \iint_{S_{out}} \left(\phi \frac{\partial\phi}{\partial n} \right) dA \quad (18)$$

This integral suggests that the closer the boundary is to the body the larger is the added mass. Furthermore, it suggests that once the boundary contributions is determined then it can be used for other bodies. Yet, this conclusion was (not) examined or noticed and hence not widely accepted and perhaps controversial without any real reasoning. Thus, when a body change his location, the value of the integral changes and hence the added mass changes.

In unscientific (not carefully measured) experiment this author conducted shows that when a floating body (styrofoam) moves toward the edge the velocity decrease. Hence, more accurate measurements are needed and this a call for others to carry this measurement.

6 The Use of The Added Mass Change

The added mass change is used in nature for various purposes which include increase the speed, changing the pivot point, increase the rotation of the body (more on this point in the next paper) etc. For example, as everyone who is swimming when approaching to the pool edge, the speed decreases and it is not an illusion. In addition to these added mass changes, the symmetry of the added mass matrix is eliminated.

One of the consequence of this analysis is that the strip theory has to be modified. In the standard method of strip theory for the slender body (a body with one dimension excessively smaller than the other two) small strip of the added mass is summed into the total added mass. The fundamental assumption in the theory is that the linearly allows to carry this summation is single strip. Even with this cause effect, the linearly is not totally lost but normal procedure has to be corrected. Consider several slices of the body (in this case the boat) in which the normal procedure, the added mass were summed linearly. In the case of the linear added mass this assume absent this correction is not proper. The regular procedure is erroneous for the added moment of inertia and thus it will not be discussed in this paper.

The body is broken in N slices for which calculation starts from slice one (1). For this slice the calculations are done as it was done in the previous procedure. For second element (slice) in addition to the calculations of the regular the effect of the previous slice has to be added. This additional term has to be done as defined in eq. (18). This requirement add some complications and tables can be made or it can be calculated directly. In ideal flow, the zero boundary condition requires normally distribution of sinks and sources in a certain arrangement. But because slice “2” already has some of the sinks and sources for slice “1” they will have to be weaker and hence the integral for slice “1” will produce a smaller value (for slice “1” as compare to the value directly calculated for “1”). For slice “3” process repeat itself and beside “2” also “1” also has to be included. It can be noticed that the face between “1” on “2” and “2” on “1” cancel each other thus only outer surface contributes with the first surface contribute of “1” that face outside. If these slices are narrow then can be neglected and only the outer of part “1” should be included. The argument is value is decrease as far slice goes from “1”. A rough estimate shows that two to three hydraulic diameter the slice can be ignored or neglected because the sources or the sinks are $\sim 1/D$ or more.

The fish and robots locomotion was mentioned, it worth to mention the energy efficiency or the possible maximum extracted energy. To generate propulsion, the fish needs on one hand to swing the tail at the largest angle (as much as possible) and create propulsion (Bar-Meir 2022a; Bar-Meir 2022b; Bar-Meir 2022c). Yet, on the other hand, the fish needs to minimize the swing as much as possible to reduce the energy loss due to the added mass effect (and negative forces). Thus, there might be one or more maximum(s) to which the fish can use. Clearly the first maximum is more likely to occur.

FIGURE 4. Strip analysis with two strip “i” and “j” in infinite medium

Concluding Remarks

In this paper it was demonstrate the additional cause of the added mass change is exist and it another object or border. Thus, when a ship approach a deck or to another ship the added mass change which causes increase of the added mass and change of direction

and slow down the ship. This cause has significance for marine and biological calculations. It also affects the calculation in area such is boiling etc. This paper is only preliminary examination of this topic. It is clear that these ideas should further explored.

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Thank you should be given to Qiang Zhu (University San Diego) when discussing on his work which led this author to realization about the current work. So even though the said work has issues, it led to better understanding of the added mass change which a thank you should be said. Zghyer, Rami pointed for decking problem which now can be explained.

About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made and on how many people plagiarized his work. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions of dollars promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing these discoveries. The irony is that these author’s models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, this servant solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation).

Kostas J. Spyrou, when he gave his keynote lecture, basically copied many concepts that were developed by Bar-Meir (such as the stability dome) and presented them as his ideas. These concepts had never appeared any the literature before. It is interesting to point out that Dr. Spyrou has been observed downloading Bar-Meir’s book. Dr. Spyrou’s behavior is not unique to him only. Dr. Kenneth Brezinsky went out of his way to declare that Bar-Meir’s calculations of compressible gas potential were useless and baseless. However, Brian J. Cantwell from Stanford University recently decided to plagiarize Bar-Meir’s idea and to dedicate a whole section (2.9) to this topic in his book (and probably also in his classes). Except that Dr. Cantwell oversimplified the idea (he removed the dimensionless presentation), maybe because he did not fully understand it. The ship stability went major

revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to the discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers' bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

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